

ALLOCATION HYBRID WSN MOBILE SENSOR NODE FOR OPTIMAL DYNAMIC COVERAGE CONTROL

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ABSTRACT

In wireless sensor networks (WSNs), coverage is an essential performance metric for monitoring delimited regions, with the allocation of sensor nodes being a critical problem for ensuring full coverage. This paper addresses the optimal allocation of mobile sensor nodes based on optimal control techniques, proposing a solution to the allocation problem, considering that the number of available nodes is sufficient to achieve full coverage. The proposed methods and algorithms for optimally allocating dynamic sensor nodes provide flawless coverage and without loss of connectivity among nodes. Based on the angular velocity of the agents, a coverage control scheme is developed, with the displacement to the specified position guaranteed by the discrete linear quadratic tracker (DLQT) and this position maintained by means of the discrete linear quadratic regulator (DLQR), in order to reduce the arrival time and residence time, respectively, in the angular position. In this scheme, the monitoring region is a delimited circle, with a static sensor node at its center. The mobile sensor nodes are positioned on a displacement circle with a radius smaller than that of the monitored region. The order of these dynamic agents along the circle is preserved to avoid collisions. Finally, the results presented indicate that the network topology, its modelling, and the proposed controller are efficient for application in monitoring hostile environments, providing greater network reliability.

KEYWORDS: Coverage Control, DLQR, DLQT, Hybrid WSN, Multi-Agent System, Optimal Control.

I. INTRODUCTION

The monitoring of environments, in a continuous and complete way, has been a research topic today. Considering that government agencies and private companies are aiming for sustainable development and are concerned about the environment and the impacts caused by industrialization, a technology capable of performing this type of monitoring, detection, and tracking of anomalies via wireless sensor networks (WSNs) is needed. The WSNs are composed of sensor nodes that can be static or mobile, each of which can contain multiple sensors and be capable of communicating and processing data locally, as discussed in [14].

Coverage of the monitored area is one of the performance criteria of WSNs, often used as an indicator of quality of service (QoS) [14] [23]. Therefore, to ensure complete and secure coverage, it is necessary to determine the type of coverage and design a strategy for allocating sensor nodes in order to use the smallest quantity of nodes and ensure a high degree of coverage of the region [23].

An alternative to increase the flexibility and robustness of dynamic coverage is to use unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) as mobile nodes to achieve optimal coverage efficiency [7], in addition to their wireless communication system presenting cost advantages and rapid deployment capabilities to communication recovery [1]. If the environment to be monitored is aquatic, underwater vehicles are available [9] [17], the agent to be used depends on the region to be monitored.

Mobile sensor nodes reduce the need for a base station, in addition to increasing the mobility and robustness of the network, despite increasing the energy consumption of the WSN. This type of node is more suitable for working on coverage control, where the objective is to direct sensor nodes to specified positions in order to optimize the detection performance of networks. In the coverage control field,

many algorithms have been developed based on the Voronoi diagram [10] [2] [6] and reinforcement learning [1] [11] [18].

The agent selected to act as a mobile sensor node will not influence the network coverage, but its position directly affects its reliability, i.e., depending on the allocation of these agents to obtain full coverage, without coverage holes and without loss of connectivity among nodes. Consequently, the coverage control of this WSN is essential to ensure reliable, full monitoring, avoiding coverage holes and loss of network communication, and ensuring good quality of service.

The WSN coverage control is considered as a sensor node localization problem, in which it can be static and offline, i.e., the optimal positions of the sensor nodes are computed offline first, and then the nodes are allocated to specified positions. Another alternative is dynamic and online coverage control, in which the sensor nodes are mobile and the control, the optimal position at that instant in time, is computed online and adjusted according to the specified criteria [14]. In their book, Selmic et al. [14] state that the optimal coverage control problem can be formulated as a linear quadratic regulator (LQR) problem, where the objective is to find the optimal position of the agents considering a focus point at which the sensor nodes must converge; the cost function aims to minimize the distance among the sensor nodes and the focus point and maximize the distance among the agents.

Coverage control of a circular WSN is a typical case of 1D coverage control, which can be applied to many practical scenarios [21]. Therefore, any geometric shape of the area of interest can be covered by one or a set of circular networks in order to provide full coverage.

The allocation of sensor nodes is a critical issue in WSNs, since it is directly related to QoS. This allocation problem can be minimized with a hybrid WSN, considering the influence of external disturbances, such as wind [3]. Another way of trying to get around this problem is to identify coverage holes, and this search can be performed using the Voronoi diagram [2]. Then, strategies to reduce and/or eliminate holes in the coverage of the region of interest can be proposed.

The deployment of the sensor nodes that make up the WSN in the region of interest is a crucial factor for the quality of monitoring. Considering two scenarios with the same quantity of sensor nodes, differences in the allocation of these nodes generate variations in the coverage and connectivity of the network. Therefore, determining the optimal position of the sensor nodes in the monitoring region. In addition, a strategy to maintain these nodes in their positions, even in the presence of external disturbances, is essential for secure coverage.

Consequently, the aim of this paper is to present the development of optimal coverage control that is constituted by dynamic and static sensor nodes, in which the control is planned offline, according to the specified design criteria. As a result, it provides the allocation and permanence of mobile sensor nodes in their specified positions to achieve full coverage. This methodology allows the monitoring of hostile environments, contributing to the ecosystems preservation, where it aims to mitigate the harmful effects caused to the environment by human beings.

The innovation and originality of the proposed methodology lie in the development of methods for optimal control of dynamic coverage for monitoring hostile environments via hybrid WSN. The methodology performs the mathematical modeling of the hybrid WSN based on graph theory and employs optimal control techniques for the allocation and regulation of the movement of mobile agents. In this way, the proposed methodology proposes a solution to a critical problem in WSN, which is the implementation of sensor nodes, i.e., allocating the nodes in their optimal positions, in order to guarantee full coverage of the circular monitoring region, in addition to guaranteeing network connectivity. Consequently, this hybrid WSN topology can be applied to monitoring aquatic ecosystems and environmental disaster areas.

The remainder of the paper is organized into seven sections. Section II presents the state of the art regarding optimal coverage control and the allocation of WSN sensor nodes. Section III describes the problem formulation, where considerations of the proposed coverage scheme are presented. Section IV presents the mathematical modeling of the hybrid WSN presented in the previous section. An optimal dynamic coverage control scheme for the hybrid WSN that ensures full coverage is presented in Section V. Section VI presents the results and discussions, where the data obtained from the computational

experiments are analyzed regarding the displacement and regulation of the agent in its specified position. Finally, Section VII presents the conclusion of the work, highlighting the contributions of the research.

II. RELATED WORKS

Regarding coverage control, Song et al. [19] [18] developed two studies. The first one was about the optimal allocation of dynamic nodes, with different maximum displacement speeds, in a delimited region that was a circle. The objective was to achieve the final configuration of the sensor network so that each dynamic sensor reaches the specified position in the shortest time; the distributed control law was used to perform this task. The second study addressed the problem of coverage control in sensor networks consisting of dynamic nodes, restricted to a circular domain and subject to position measurement errors. The objective, as in the previous study, is to minimize the response time of the sensor nodes to reach any point on the monitored circumference. However, this coverage control law reduces or even eliminates the effect of measurement errors, i.e., these errors cannot affect coverage performance.

The circular formation is an important topic for the blanket control problem. It is a geometric arrangement commonly used in multi-agent systems, positioning the agents equidistantly around a central point. This type of formation has been widely explored in several applications, such as area coverage and cooperative monitoring, especially in WSN, as presented in the following related works.

In the study conducted by Wang et al. [20], the authors investigated the circular formation of dynamic agents, with emphasis on maintaining the order of the agents along the entire trajectory. The objective was to preserve the initial configuration, avoiding collisions during the coordinated circular motion. In another work, Wang et al. [22], the measurement error is added in relation to the position that the sensor detects from its adjacent neighbors, in addition to proving that the proposed distributed control law leads the system to the desired formation, even with noisy measurements of the agents' positions.

In the same line of research, Feng et al. [4] worked with the formation control for a mobile sensor network with limited position measurement errors, in which the sensor nodes are required to perform a determined formation in a circle. They solved this problem in two steps. In the first step, an estimation algorithm was proposed to estimate the position difference between sensors and their neighbors. In the second step, they proposed a distributed circle formation control law for each sensor, using the estimated position difference, showing that the effect of measurement error in the circle formation is reduced.

The placement of sensor nodes is directly related to the coverage and connectivity requirements of the WSN. Therefore, determining the precise position of agents directly impacts network performance. In [13], the authors developed an algorithm for estimating the distance among sensor nodes, based on the relationship between the distance and the density of nodes distributed in the monitored region. In addition, they took into account the connectivity status of the sensors.

Considering the constraints of order permanence and maximum speed of each agent, the authors [21] developed cooperative coverage control laws for each mobile sensor node with dual integrator dynamics, subject to unknown and bounded disturbances. The objective of this research is to minimize the coverage cost function, where the aim is to minimize the arrival time.

In [15], the authors treat the coverage problem as the coordination of multiple agents to cover an unknown area in an optimized manner; the network modeling is based on Voronoi tessellation. Two controller structures based on the tracking predictive control (MPC) model are proposed: the first, called two-layer, includes a block of references that are computed by the server and are inputs to the individual MPC of each agent. The second is called a one-layer structure; it does not have the references, i.e., the calculation of the next optimal configuration is directly inserted into the MPC cost of each agent, and it is based on the Bayesian optimization method.

In [8], the coverage and energy consumption problems for underwater acoustic sensor networks are reported, and a method based on the improved snake optimizer is proposed. In the proposed method, the sensor nodes are first distributed according to the characteristics of the marine monitoring area, with the algorithm based on the analytical hierarchy process. In the second step, to minimize energy

consumption and maximize coverage, the improved snake optimizer algorithm, which is based on adversarial learning, is proposed. Finally, the proposed method also consists of a path allocation strategy to reallocate the sensor nodes, providing efficient coverage and equalizing the energy consumption for the nodes.

Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) have been widely employed for monitoring remote areas. In [1], UAVs were utilized to construct a Wireless Sensor Network (WSN), addressing the limitations related to energy constraints and communication range. The authors proposed an autonomous and energy-efficient dynamic displacement planning by incorporating a new type of pheromone into the multi-agent reinforcement learning framework. The trait pheromone model is integrated with the stigmergy mechanism to simulate natural pheromones, enhancing the internal indirect communications between agents and avoiding network delay.

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION

This work proposes the optimal dynamic coverage control, based on the optimal allocation and regulation of mobile sensor nodes in their specified positions, ensuring full coverage, without holes and loss of connectivity among agents. The detection model used is the binary disk model, as illustrated in Figure 1, where the sensor sensitivity is determined by a circumference and the points inside it are fully covered. Consequently, any target that is inside this disk is detected, facilitating coverage planning, in addition to its efficiency in applying coverage with any geometry. The network topology used is the hybrid star-ring, shown in Figure 1, which has attributes of both the star and ring topologies.

Figure 1. Coverage scheme, without holes, with mobile sensor nodes and a static sensor node, with the delimitation of the monitoring region \mathbb{S} , the mobile nodes move on the S circumference, and the detection and connectivity circumferences of the sensor nodes have radius $r_s = r_c$.

Consequently, consider a hybrid WSN with i mobile agents, where $i \in I_N = \{1, \dots, N\}$. This network consists of $N + 1$ sensor nodes, the last is a static node and the N dynamic nodes. The mobile sensor nodes are allocated in the S circle of radius r and the static sensor node is allocated in the center of S , as illustrated in Figure 1. The region to be monitored is also a \mathbb{S} circumference of radius R . Assume that q_i is the angular position of each agent that is determined in the counterclockwise direction from the positive horizontal axis. A limiting factor of this sensor network is the detection radius of the sensors r_s and the connectivity radius r_c , to avoid coverage holes, originating from an unmonitored region or a loss of communication among the agents. Also consider that all sensors have the same detection and connectivity radius, and that these two radius are equal $r_s = r_c$.

Each sensor node has information about the angular position (q_i) and velocity (ω_i) of its adjacent neighbors, where the two neighbors of agent i are denoted by

$$i^+ = \begin{cases} i + 1, & \text{if } i = 1, \dots, N - 1 \\ 1, & \text{if } i = N \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

and

$$i^- = \begin{cases} N, & \text{if } i = 1 \\ i - 1, & \text{if } i = 2, \dots, N \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where i^+ is the right-adjacent neighbor, and i^- is the left-adjacent neighbor of agent i and N is the number of mobile sensor nodes and all dynamic agents have information about the position of the static sensor, located at the center of the circle (0,0). The distance between sensor node i and its immediate neighbor i^+ , in the counterclockwise direction, at time k is defined by $d_i(k)$, assuming values in the interval $[0, 2\pi r)$ and $\sum_{i=1}^N d_i(k) = 2\pi r$ m, is given by

$$d_i(k) = d(q_i(k), q_j(k)) = \begin{cases} q_j(k) - q_i(k), & \text{if } q_j(k) \geq q_i(k) \\ q_j(k) - q_i(k) + 2\pi r, & \text{if } q_j(k) < q_i(k) \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

and

$$d_{N+1}(k) = d(q_{N+1}(k), q_i(k)) = \{q_i(k) - q_{N+1}(k), \text{ se } i = 1, \dots, N. \quad (4)$$

In this paper, the hybrid WSN is mathematically modeled using graph theory $G(V, E)$ [12], where V are nodes that are the vertices of the graph, E are the edges, i.e., the angular distance between the sensor i and its neighbors that are immediately behind and in front (i^-, i^+), with $i = 1, \dots, N$. Consequently, the graph describing this relationship is undirected, with $V = \{1, 2, 3, \dots, N, N + 1\}$ and $E = \{(1, 2), (1, N), (1, N + 1), \dots, (i, i^+), (i, i^-), (i, N + 1), \dots, (N, 1), (N, N - 1), (N, N + 1), (N + 1, 1), \dots, (N + 1, N)\}$.

This formulation is oriented towards the optimal control of dynamic coverage to minimize/eliminate coverage holes, which are related to the allocation of mobile sensor nodes, and maintain the connectivity of the hybrid WSN, avoiding communication failure. Consequently, this is an optimal control problem, where the cost function of interest minimizes the time that the mobile sensor node reaches and remains in the specified angular position.

IV. MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF HYBRID WSN

The proposed hybrid WSN is a multi-agent system whose main objective is to provide coverage without holes, taking into account the control effort. The mathematical modeling of this system is based on graph theory, since the various sensor nodes operate together to achieve the goal of full monitoring.

Considering that the dynamic sensor nodes move in a single direction, counterclockwise, with different angular velocities $\omega_i(k) \neq \omega_{i+1}(k) \neq \dots \neq \omega_N(k)$ for $i = 1, \dots, N$ and that the sensor node $N + 1$ has a zero velocity $\omega_{N+1}(k) = 0$. This modeling takes into account that each sensor node has information about the position and angular velocity of neighboring sensor nodes, as illustrated in Figure 2. Consequently, the information flow in this graph is undirected, since agent i is detected by both agent i^+ and agent i^- , in addition to agent $N + 1$. Therefore, information flows in three directions.

The control effort is denoted by u_i , is a linear combination of the states, and when divided by the gain, represents the angular velocity of the dynamic agents, i.e., at the discrete time instant k , the velocity of agent i is given by $\omega_i(k) = u_i(k)/\kappa$, where κ is a constant that transforms u into angular velocity rad/s.

The static sensor node is located at the center of the displacement circle, while the dynamic sensors move around it in circular trajectories. During this circular movement, there is a vector that points to the center of the trajectory, resulting in variations in the direction and sense of the angular velocity of the agents. This phenomenon is known as centripetal acceleration, expressed by $a_{cp} = r\omega^2$ m/s², where r is the radius of the circle and ω represents the angular velocity of the agent.

Figure 2. Schematic of the hybrid WSN model with its representations of position, distance, and angular velocity and the relationship of agents with their adjacent neighbors.

According to Figure 2, the control laws for this proposed hybrid WSN, which consists of a static sensor node at the center of the S circle and N mobile sensor nodes located along the S circle, are computed from the angular velocities of its adjacent neighbors and the centripetal acceleration relative to the static node. The control laws of the mobile nodes are given by

$$u_1(k) = (\omega_1(k) + \omega_N(k))(q_2(k) - q_1(k)) - (\omega_1(k) + \omega_2(k))(q_1(k) - q_N(k) + 2\pi r) + r\omega_1^2(k)(q_{N+1}(k) - q_1(k)), \quad (5)$$

$$u_i(k) = (\omega_i(k) + \omega_{i-}(k))(q_{i+}(k) - q_i(k)) - (\omega_i(k) + \omega_{i+}(k))(q_i(k) - q_{i-}(k)) + r\omega_i^2(k)(q_{N+1}(k) - q_i(k)) \quad (6)$$

and

$$u_N(k) = (\omega_{N-1}(k) + \omega_N(k))(q_1(k) - q_N(k) + 2\pi r) - (\omega_1(k) + \omega_N(k))(q_N(k) - q_{N-1}(k)) + r\omega_1^2(k)(q_{N+1}(k) - q_N(k)), \quad (7)$$

where $\omega_i(k)$ is the angular velocity, $q_i(k)$ is the angular position of agent i at a time instant k and r is the radius of the displacement S circle. By developing the equations, Eq. (5) to Eq. (7), the control efforts are given by

$$u_1(k) = -(2\omega_1(k) + r\omega_1^2(k) + \omega_2(k) + \omega_N(k))q_1(k) + (\omega_1(k) + \omega_N(k))q_2(k) + (\omega_1(k) + \omega_2(k))q_N(k) + r\omega_1^2(k)q_{N+1}(k) - (\omega_1(k) + \omega_N(k))2\pi r, \quad (8)$$

$$u_i(k) = (\omega_i(k) + \omega_{i+}(k))q_{i-}(k) - (\omega_{i-}(k) + 2\omega_i(k) + r\omega_i^2(k) + \omega_{i+}(k))q_i(k) + (\omega_{i-}(k) + \omega_i(k))q_{i+}(k) + r\omega_i^2(k)q_{N+1}(k), \quad i = 2, \dots, N-1 \quad (9)$$

and

$$u_N(k) = (\omega_{N-1}(k) + \omega_N(k))q_1(k) + (\omega_1(k) + \omega_N(k))q_{N-1}(k) - (\omega_1(k) + \omega_{N-1}(k) + 2\omega_N(k) + r\omega_N^2(k))q_N(k) + r\omega_N^2(k)q_{N+1}(k) + (\omega_{N-1}(k) + \omega_N(k))2\pi r, \quad (10)$$

According to Eq. (8) to Eq. (10), $u_i(k)$ is the control effort given in relation to the angular velocity of the agents. Since these sensor nodes are organized in a circle, an adjustment of $2\pi r$ is added when calculating the distance of the first and last agent in the circle. These equations are obtained through graph theory and are important because they represent the dynamics of the system.

Considering that the sensor node $N + 1$ is static and is at the center of the displacement S circle, its control effort $u_{N+1}(k)$ is given by

$$u_{N+1}(k) = 0, \quad \forall k \geq 0. \quad (11)$$

By arranging Eq. (8) to Eq. (11) in matrix form, the control laws are given by

$$u(k) = -L(k)q(k) + F(k), \quad (12)$$

where $q(k) = [q_1(k), q_2(k), \dots, q_i(k), \dots, q_N(k), q_{N+1}(k)]^T$, the column vector of states, which are the angular positions of the sensor nodes and $L(k) \in \mathfrak{R}^{(N+1) \times (N+1)}$ is the Laplacian matrix, with the angular velocities of the agents that are given by

$$L(k) = \begin{bmatrix} 2\omega_1 + r\omega_1^2 + \omega_2 + \omega_N & -(\omega_1 + \omega_N) & 0 & \dots & 0 & -(\omega_1 + \omega_2) & -r\omega_1^2 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & -(\omega_i + \omega_{i+}) & \omega_i - 2\omega_i + r\omega_i^2 + \omega_{i+} & -(\omega_i - \omega_i) & \dots & -r\omega_i^2 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ -(\omega_{N-1} + \omega_N) & \dots & 0 & \dots & -(\omega_1 + \omega_N) & \omega_1 + \omega_{N-1} + 2\omega_N + r\omega_N^2 & -r\omega_N^2 \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & \dots & \dots & 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (13)$$

Still according to Eq. (12), $F(k) \in \mathfrak{R}^{N+1}$ is a vector given by

$$F(k) = [-(\omega_1(k) + \omega_2(k))2\pi r \quad \dots \quad 0 \quad \dots \quad 0 \quad (\omega_{N-1}(k) + \omega_N(k))2\pi r \quad 0]^T. \quad (14)$$

V. OPTIMAL CONTROL OF DYNAMIC COVERAGE

The hybrid WSN proposed in this paper has a static sensor node at the center of the circular monitoring region and mobile sensor nodes located on the displacement circumference, with a radius smaller than the radius of the monitoring area. Therefore, for this purpose, the optimal discrete controllers DLQT and DLQR modified for the hybrid WSN are implemented.

According to Section IV, which deals with the mathematical modeling of the hybrid WSN, the discrete-time dynamic equation of the position of the agents is given by

$$q(k+1) = f(q(k), u(k), r), \quad (15)$$

where $f \in \mathfrak{R}^{N+1}$ is a vector relating the control effort $u(k)$ and the angular position $q(k)$. The Eq. (15) which in explicit form is given by

$$q(k+1) = -L(k)q(k) + Bu(k) + F(k), \quad (16)$$

where $B \in \mathfrak{R}^{(N+1) \times (N+1)}$ is the constant weighting matrix of the control effort vector. Considering the initial condition as $q(0)$, this equation of the system dynamics represents a constraint, determining the state at time $(k+1)$, from the state and control at time k .

The theory of optimal control proposes the minimization of a system performance index from the calculated optimal control effort $u^*(k)$. The coverage control problem, according to [14], is formulated as a discrete linear quadratic regulator (DLQR). In this work, the implementation of the discrete linear quadratic tracker (DLQT) and DLQR controllers is proposed, with the objective of moving and preserving the sensor nodes in their specified positions, respectively. The DLQT and DLQR are modified in order to determine the angular velocity required for each sensor node to reach and maintain its position in the presence of disturbances, minimizing the time spent for this. Therefore, the function to minimize the performance index is given by

$$V^*(q(k)) = \min_u J(q(k), \omega(k), r), \quad (17)$$

where $J = \sum_{k=i}^{\infty} q(k)^T Q q(k) + u(k)^T R u(k)$ is the performance index to be minimized that depends on the current state $q(k)$, the angular velocities $\omega(k)$ and the radius of the displacement circle r . The solution of J is the semidefinite positive Lyapunov function, i.e., $J = q(k)^T P(k) q(k)$. Considering the dynamics of the hybrid WSN (Eq. (16)), and the quadratic performance index J , the Bellman equation for DLQR is given by

$$q(k)^T P(k) q(k) = q(k)^T Q q(k) + u(k)^T R u(k) + (-L(k)q(k) + Bu(k) + F(k))^T P(k+1) (-L(k)q(k) + Bu(k) + F(k)), \quad (18)$$

where the matrices $Q \in \mathfrak{R}^{(N+1) \times (N+1)}$, $R \in \mathfrak{R}^{(N+1) \times (N+1)}$ are weighting matrices and $P(k)$ is the solution of the discrete Algebraic Riccati Equation (DARE). The matrix Q directly interferes in the system states $q(k)$, while the matrix R interferes in the control effort $u(k) \in \mathfrak{R}^{N+1}$, which divided by the gain κ , refers to the angular velocity of the agent. As it is proposed to reduce the arrival time to the specified position from the velocity of the mobile sensor nodes. A transformation matrix $D(k) \in \mathfrak{R}^{(N+1) \times (N+1)}$, which expresses the distance of the agents and their adjacent neighbors, is added to aid in the algebraic manipulations. This matrix is constructed from Eq. (3) and Eq. (4), in order to operate with angular velocity and time, where $D(k)$ is given by

$$D(k) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & (q_2(k) - q_1(k)) & 0 & \dots & 0 & (q_N(k) - q_1(k) + 2\pi r) & r \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & (q_i^-(k) - q_i(k)) & 1 & (q_i^+(k) - q_i(k)) & \dots & r \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ (q_1(k) - q_N(k) + 2\pi r) & \dots & 0 & \dots & (q_{N-1}(k) - q_n(k)) & 1 & r \\ r & \dots & r & \dots & r & \dots & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

According to Eq. (19), r is the radius of the agents' displacement region, and q_i is the angular position of the sensor node i . To reformulate the classical DLQR, from the matrix $D(k)$, the constant κ , and defining $\tilde{u}(k) = D(k)^{-1} \frac{u(k)}{\kappa}$, the cost function of Eq. (18) is written as

$$q(k)^T P(k) q(k) = q(k)^T Q q(k) + \tilde{u}(k)^T R \tilde{u}(k) + (-L(k)q(k) + B\tilde{u}(k) + F(k))^T P(k+1) (-L(k)q(k) + B\tilde{u}(k) + F(k)). \quad (20)$$

Assuming that the value is quadratic in the state and considering a steady-state feedback policy, the control effort is given by $\tilde{u}(k) = -K(k)q(k)$, where $K(k)$ is the gain matrix. Therefore, the Lyapunov equation is given by

$$P(k) = Q + K(k)^T R K(k) + (-L(k) - BK(k) + F(k)q(k)^{-1})^T P(k+1) (-L(k)q(k) - BK(k) + F(k)q(k)^{-1}). \quad (21)$$

The optimal control effort, $\tilde{u}^*(k)$, for the modified DLQR, from the partial derivative of the value function with respect to $\tilde{u}(k)$, is given by

$$\tilde{u}(k) = -(B^T P(k+1)B + R)^{-1} B^T P(k+1) L(k) q(k), \quad (22)$$

where the optimal gain matrix is $K(k) = (B^T P(k+1)B + R)^{-1} B^T P(k+1) L(k)$, according to the control law.

This formulation of the modified DLQR for the minimum time problem from the angular velocity is represented in a closed-loop block diagram in Figure 3, exposing the feedbacks and updates of the matrices, in addition to the delay z^{-1} to generate the output angular position at time instant k .

Figure 3. Block diagram of the hybrid closed-loop WSN with the optimal controller DLQT or DLQR, depending on whether the reference signal is nonzero or equal to zero, respectively.

According to Figure 3, $K(k)$ is the matrix of optimal gains, $P(k)$ is the solution of the DARE given by Eq. (22), and R is the weighting matrix of the control effort, $D(k)$ is the distance matrix, $\tilde{u}(k)$ is the control effort that represents time, $u(k) = D(k)\tilde{u}(k)\kappa$ is the control effort that represents angular velocity and that is used to update the Laplacian matrix $L(k)$ and the position adjustment vector on the circumference $F(k)$, $q(k)$ is the angular position at time instant k and $h(k)$ is the reference signal, which for the DLQR is considered null, $h(k) = 0$. The dashed arrows of the blocks of $F(k)$, $D(k)$ and $L(k)$ represent that these parameters are updated at each iteration: the matrix $D(k)$ with the output positions $q(k)$, the vector $F(k)$ and the matrix $L(k)$ with the angular velocities $u(k)/\kappa$.

Consequently, to calculate the optimal control effort $\tilde{u}^*(k)$, according to Eq. (23), where the optimal gain $K(k)$ of the modified DLQR regulates the agents in their specified positions, bypassing the disturbances, it is necessary to solve the DARE.

DLQT is an extension of DLQR, the difference is that it forces the system states to track a reference trajectory, that is, the reference signal in DLQR was null, $h(k) = 0$, while in DLQT it will receive a value specified by the designer, $h(k) \neq 0$, as illustrated in Figure 3.

Knowing that the dynamics of the system are given by Eq. (16) and that its response is given by

$$y(k) = Cq(k), \tag{23}$$

where $y(k) \in \mathfrak{R}^{N+1}$ is the vector with the angular velocities of the agents, and $C \in \mathfrak{R}^{(N+1) \times (N+1)}$ is the output vector of the system. This system does not have a built-in integrator. Therefore, it is necessary to develop the augmented model of the hybrid WSN, with a built-in integrator, so that the steady-state error is zero.

For DLQT, the cost function [16], given by Eq. (18), is rewritten as

$$J_i = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=i}^{\infty} [(y(k) - h(k))^T Q (y(k) - h(k)) + \Delta \tilde{u}(k)^T R \tilde{u}(k)], \tag{24}$$

where Q is a positive semidefinite Hermitian matrix ($Q \geq 0$), R is a positive definite Hermitian matrix ($R > 0$) and $P(k)$ is a positive semidefinite matrix ($P(k) \geq 0$). Considering the difference of the state variable as $\Delta q(k) = q(k) - q(k - 1)$, with Δ being the first-order difference operator, the difference of the control variable is given by $\Delta \tilde{u}(k) = \tilde{u}(k) - \tilde{u}(k - 1)$. The output equation, Eq. (23) is rewritten as

$$y(k) = y(k - 1) + C \Delta q(k), \tag{25}$$

Therefore, by augmenting the systems model, Eq. (16) with Eq. (25) and organizing it in matrix form, the new augmented state-space model is given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta q(k + 1) \\ y(k) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -L(k) & 0_{(N+1) \times (N+1)} \\ C & I_{(N+1) \times (N+1)} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta q(k) \\ y(k - 1) \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} B \\ 0_{(N+1) \times (N+1)} \end{bmatrix} \Delta \tilde{u}(k), \tag{26}$$

and

$$y(k) = [C \quad I_{(N+1) \times (N+1)}] \begin{bmatrix} \Delta q(k) \\ y(k - 1) \end{bmatrix}, \tag{27}$$

where I is the identity matrix. Considering $h(k)$ to be a constant and nonzero reference signal, Eq. (27) is rewritten as

$$y(k) - h = y(k - 1) - h + C \Delta q(k), \tag{28}$$

Consequently, the augmented state-space model Eq. (26) and Eq. (27) is rewritten as

$$\underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \Delta q(k + 1) \\ y(k) - h \end{bmatrix}}_{\tilde{q}(k+1)} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} -L(k) & 0_{(N+1) \times (N+1)} \\ C & I_{(N+1) \times (N+1)} \end{bmatrix}}_{\tilde{L}(k)} \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \Delta q(k) \\ y(k - 1) - h \end{bmatrix}}_{\tilde{q}(k)} + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} B \\ 0_{(N+1) \times (N+1)} \end{bmatrix}}_{\tilde{B}} \Delta \tilde{u}(k), \tag{29}$$

and

$$\frac{y(k) - h}{\bar{y}(k)} = \frac{[C \quad I_{(N+1) \times (N+1)}]}{\bar{c}} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta q(k) \\ y(k-1) - h \end{bmatrix} \frac{1}{\bar{q}(k)} \tag{30}$$

The performance index of Eq. (25) is given by

$$J_i = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=i}^{\infty} \tilde{q}(k)^T \tilde{Q} \tilde{q}(k) + \Delta \tilde{u}(k)^T R \Delta \tilde{u}(k), \tag{31}$$

where $\tilde{Q} = \tilde{C}^T Q \tilde{C}$. The optimal control effort $\Delta \tilde{u}(k)$, which will minimize the performance index Eq. (31) is given by

$$\Delta \tilde{u}(k) = -K(k) \Delta q(k), \tag{32}$$

where $K(k)$ is the optimal gains, calculated through the matrix $P(k)$ which is the solution to the DARE [5], and is given by

$$K(k) = -R^{-1} \tilde{B}^T P(k). \tag{33}$$

Figure 3 represents the block diagram of the hybrid WSN in a closed loop with the optimal controller DLQT, so that the agents are allocated optimally in their specified positions, minimizing the arrival time to that point. Therefore, reducing energy consumption and increasing the lifetime of the mobile sensor node. When comparing this diagram with that of the DLQT, it is observed that the difference is the non-zero reference signal, $h(k) \neq 0$.

The optimal control structure proposed in this paper aims at the optimal allocation of mobile sensor nodes in the displacement circumference to ensure full monitoring of the circular area of interest, without coverage holes and without loss of connectivity among agents. In Figure 4, this methodology is presented in the form of a block diagram.

Figure 4. Proposed scheme for the optimal allocation of mobile sensor nodes, ensuring full coverage, without holes and without loss of connectivity.

According to Figure 4, the first block is the angular position of the sensor nodes that is input to the optimal dynamic coverage controller, which is constituted by the modified DLQT, to move the agents to their specified positions, followed by the modified DLQR, to regulate the agents in their positions in order to bypass external disturbances.

VI. RESULTS

The results obtained in this article aim to optimally allocate mobile agents in order to provide full coverage, without holes and without loss of connectivity among agents, in addition to minimizing the agents' travel time, extending the sensor nodes' lifetime.

Considering that we want to monitor a circle with radius $R = 4$ m, the sensor detection radius is equal to the connectivity radius $r_s = r_c = 3$ m and the radius of the displacement circle is $r = 3.5$ m. For this hybrid WSN, the number of mobile sensor nodes is four, considering that there is a static sensor node at the center of the circle. Therefore, the network consists of five sensor nodes.

The agents are labeled in a counterclockwise direction according to their initial positions in the circle and each agent has a maximum speed. The initial position of each agent is given by $[0.033 \ 0.837 \ 1.640 \ 2.443 \ 0]^T$ rad, the last position of the static sensor node, which is located at the center of the circle. The angular velocity of the sensor nodes is $[0.10 \ 0.10 \ 0.10 \ 0.10 \ 0]^T$ rad/s, the last velocity is of the static node, so it is 0 rad/s. Figure 5 shows the sensor nodes in their initial position, on the displacement circumference. Applying the modified DLQT in steady state, with the transformation constant $\kappa = 10$, the weighting matrices Q and R used were the identity, and the desired final positions of the agents are $[1.832 \ 3.665 \ 5.497 \ 7.330 \ 0]^T$ rad. Figure 6 illustrates the displacement of the mobile sensor nodes from their initial position.

Figure 5. The initial positions of the five sensor nodes, where the mobile sensor nodes are allocated along the S circumference with a radius of $r = 3.5$ m.

Figure 6. The displacement of the five sensor nodes in the displacement S circle, to the specified angular position, with radius $r = 3.5$ m, where the four dynamic agents are uniformly distributed in S and the static sensor node is located in the center.

Analyzing Figure 6, it is observed that the mobile nodes move, but maintain the order, in order to avoid collisions, in addition to reaching the specified position in approximately $k = 4$ iterations, with the following angular positions $[5.497 \ 10.996 \ 16.493 \ 21.991 \ 0]^T$ m, where an error tolerance of 0.001 m was considered. The control effort that performed this displacement is illustrated in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Evolution of the control effort, angular velocity, responsible for the displacement of the five sensor nodes in the displacement S circumference, to the specified angular position, with radius $r = 3.5$ m.

According to Figure 7, the dynamic agents started their movement with zero angular velocities, and in order to approach the specified position, their velocities increased until they reached their specified positions. The expected velocity for the agents to reach their specified positions, according to Eq. (16), considering that $F(k)$ is constant and will not influence the system, is given by $[1.292 \ 11.380 \ 17.071 \ 27.159 \ 0]^T$ rad/s. When compared with the velocities reached by the agents, according to Figure 7, the first and fourth mobile sensor nodes did not reach the maximum velocities, presenting a tolerance of ± 5 rad/s.

With the sensor nodes in their specified position, in order to provide full coverage, the DLQR controller is applied to ensure that the mobile sensor nodes remain in their positions, maintaining monitoring without coverage holes and without loss of connectivity among the agents.

The optimal DLQR controller was also implemented in the hybrid WSN. In steady state, the weighting matrices Q and R were the identity, the constant $\kappa = 10$, the vector of the initial positions of the agents that is the final specified is $[5.497 \ 10.996 \ 16.493 \ 21.991 \ 0]^T$ m. Figure 8 illustrates the sensor nodes uniformly distributed in the displacement circumference, providing full coverage, and the modified DLQR controller is implemented to keep the mobile nodes in these positions.

Figure 8. Desired position of the five sensor nodes on the displacement S circle, with radius $r = 3.5$ m, where the four agents are uniformly distributed in S and the static sensor node is located in the center, providing full coverage.

The modified DLQR controller was applied considering the same angular velocities as the modified DLQT. Figure 9 illustrates the evolution of the angular position of the five agents, with their reference signal being zero, that is, they must remain in their initial positions, which are the specified positions.

Figure 9. Evolution of the angular position of the five sensor nodes in the displacement S circumference, with radius $r = 3.5$ m, where DLQR is applied to regulate the position of the agents, keeping the sensor nodes in their specified positions, controlling external disturbances from the environment.

According to Figure 9, the five mobile sensor nodes went to zero, that is, they remained in their initial position, where each agent went to its zero, remaining in their specified positions. Figure 10 shows the control effort related to the displacement shown in Figure 9.

Figure 10. Evolution of the control effort, angular velocity, with the modified DLQR controller, responsible for keeping the five sensor nodes in their specified angular positions on the displacement S circle.

According to Figure 10, observing that after the mobile sensor nodes reached their zeros, the control effort also went to zero, approximately at time $k = 2$, representing that the sensor nodes remained in their final positions. Consequently, the monitoring configuration presented in Figure 8 is maintained.

VII. CONCLUSION

Aiming at optimal control of dynamic coverage, i.e., monitoring without coverage holes and without loss of connectivity among the sensor nodes that constitute a hybrid WSN, an optimal method to allocate and regulate the specified positions of our mobile sensors for full monitoring of a given circular region was presented in this paper. Then, a mathematical modeling of the allocations of the sensor nodes of this network was performed, based on graph theory and taking into account the position, angular velocity and centripetal traction of both the mobile nodes and the static node.

The proposed method for allocating our mobile sensors was shown to be efficient in the construction of the hybrid WSN, with a sensor node in the center of the monitoring region. That is, the DLQR modified the optimal control efforts to move the agents until they reach their specified positions, minimizing the time to achieve the final construction of the network, based on the angular velocities of the agents. Considering that the quantity of our mobile sensors is sufficient to cover the entire circular area of interest, this method ensures full coverage, without loss of connectivity among the sensor nodes.

Another advantage of this proposed method is the modified DLQR implementation to maintain the network formation, in order to guarantee full coverage. This method also seeks to minimize the time it takes for the agent to return to its position after a disturbance. This increases the reliability of the hybrid WSN, ensuring that any anomaly in the monitoring area is detected.

Consequently, the hybrid WSN model and the method for allocation and regulation of our mobile sensors have shown that they proved to be satisfactory monitor hostile environments, difficult to access environments or any region of interest, increasing the reliability of the network. In this case, the sensors capture information that can be processed by each node or at a base station for specific decision-making.

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